

THE ROLE OF INEFFICIENT METHODS IN THE FORMATION OF TERMS AND NEOLOGISMS RELATED TO PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article covers the classification and detailed explanations of less productive(or inefficient) methods in the derivation of sports and physical education terms in English. Additionally, extensive information is provided with detailed, concrete examples of a number of less productive term generating methods such as Phonological method, Soinage method, Clipping, conversion. In this work, we study the comparative analysis of inefficient methods in the formation of lexical units related to PES in English.

Key words: phonological method, soinage method, clipping, conversion, back formation, multiple process.

Phonological method. A very rare, more inactive method of creating a new word is the phonological method. In English, words made in this way are unusual, rude, and very resonant in their expression. This phenomenon is also called echoism (echoism), symbolism (symbolism), onomatopoeia (simulated sound). These lexical units are formed on the basis of whether unusual sounds give a specific goal-oriented sign or gesture and express their purpose through the emotional actions of the individual. In addition, they appear in imitation of the sound of movements in sports. Lexical units created by the phonetic method more express the emotion of the individual. There are also such units among the lexical units related to physical

education and sports. For example, in 1823, a ping-pong-ping-pong lexical unit appeared in China to mimic the sounds that make a blow in table tennis. At the 2016 European Football Championship, the Icelandic national team turned to the fans after each match, raised their hands and applauded, chanting "Huux-xuux-xuux !!!" applauded. As a result, this Hoooh - hoooh! - Xuux - xuux! the shout turned into a sports-related unit.

Lexical units that phonologically interpret PES terms in Uzbek are very rare. Including: no, this unit is the name of a test that tests the physical abilities of athletes (this word belongs to the Filipino language). Although not included in the terms of PES, dii-diit belongs to the child's speech! Or boom-boom! - Units are applied to the car. Tir-tir-tir! - Represents the sound of a motorcycle. Phonological units in English are often called phonological neologisms because they are not present in the dictionary. The phonological method is very rare in the field of Uzbek language PES. Since it is transferred from other languages to Uzbek without change, it is often accepted as borrowing. Etymology is a method of etymology: J.Yule notes that many field terms in English come from Latin. Other languages have also contributed to the development of English .In linguistics, the formation of words using the method of etymology is common. The word etymology is derived from the ancient Greek word 'etymon - "original form" + logia - "study of". The method of etymology is a process that can express a particular concept that arises in the process of studying the history of existing terms, giving rise to pre-existing secondary units as primary. In this method, the transition of lexical units formed from the specific to the general according to the meaning and purpose is observed. Through this process, a word or term becomes a common property again and takes a permanent place in the vocabulary of a particular language. This method is available in both languages being compared. If we take a closer look at the method of etymology, we can observe many terms related to the field of PES, which appeared several hundred years ago, both in English and in Uzbek. Naturally, the most important process in such terms is the phenomenon of changes in speech sounds. That is, a particular term over time encounters accommodation, dissimilation, haplology, dieresis, and other phonetic

phenomena. For example; The English term golf is derived from the Scottish term bata, gouf, cluba; uzb. "game") formed by the addition of language units. As a result of the etymological approach to the term, gouf was chosen as an alternative lexical unit in English, which has gone through certain phonetic stages in its current form of golf. In the initial and present form of the term, two different phenomena of sound change are observed. The first is the reduction of the vowel in the Scottish goof unit during the reduction process, and the second is the phenomenon of epenthesis (gain in the word structure), i.e. the increase in the l sound in the English golf terminological unit. As a result, the current term golf is morphologically formed in the form of gouf ↔ golf as a term formed from a word belonging to the horse family N → N, belonging to the horse family.

The original form of the term tennis was "la paulme". The game is so named because in the Middle Ages, French knights played the ball with their hands (palms). This type of game is literally translated into English as the palm. The main rule of the game is tenez in the command form of the French tenir verb! is expressed in English as hold! receive! take!, "that is", "hold!", "accept!", "take!" meanings. As a result of an etymological approach since 1874, the term la paulme has been mastered by the British in the form of tenez, i.e. tennis, under the name of its basic rule. This term has encountered two different types of sound changes in its original and present form. The first is the phenomenon of epenthesis, that is, the increase of n sounds in the lexical unit of tennis. The phenomenon of assimilation (mutual adaptation of sounds), i.e. the change of sound due to the similarity of ez in the French tense unit to the work in the English tennis lexical unit, is observed. As a result, the term tennis is used today. Morphologically, tenez → tennis, V → N, i.e. the change of the verb to the noun phrase is observed.

From the above examples, we can observe that the terms PES have functionally changed from specific to general.

The process of formation of terms based on the method of etymology is also observed in the Uzbek language. The similarity in the compared languages is that the development of PES terms in English, the influence of Latin, Greek, French, German

played an important role in the expansion of the vocabulary, while the Uzbek language was enriched by lexical units learned from Arabic, Persian, Russian and Mongolian.

For example: a slingshot is a weapon that throws a stone into it. This lexeme, which exists in our language, is used as the Persian palahmon. As a result of the study of ancient written sources by linguists, this lexical unit has been recorded as the name of a sports equipment. The right of the orphan, the arrow of the scepter (proverb).

Although discus throwing (ancient Greek Olympic Games; first competition in Germany, 1870) has a long history, it became popular in our country in the second half of the last century. In the ancient Greeks, the unit disk - discus (discus) meant a heavy circle flat stone. The term disk, which was introduced into Uzbek through Russian, is still widely used in communication. As the term disk is used to refer to a heavy circle as a flat stone, as a result of the post-independence etymological approach, the word lappak stone (flat, flat, flat stone) was called in Uzbek and over time the word stone was dropped. As a result, morphologically there was a splash of quality - the word lappak was used instead of the word lappak stone. Functionally, the leppak (adjective) lexical unit has morphological features performed by the stone (at) lexical unit, which changes through possessive, accusative, plural affixes. This lexical unit is expressed in some sources as lapp + ak = lappak (a horse formed by adding an adjective). But in the process of studying annotated and other terminological dictionaries, we could not find a lap or lapp core. Therefore, lappak is an Adj → N, i.e. adjective horse term.

This term has formed around itself several PES-related compound terms. For example, terms such as lappak shooter, lappak throw area, lappak area are among them.

Soinage method. Another common word-formation method in English is the coinage method. The origin of words by this method is present not only in English, but also in most terminological systems of the Uzbek language, in particular, in the terminology of PES. The creation of new lexical units using the Coinej method is a new and unique common name that has been identified or given in relation to newly

produced products for a particular industry. These names are also commonly called brand names and are written in lower case. The fact that neologisms related to PES are formed precisely by the coinage method is quite significant. For example: Frisbee - Frisbee is the name of a sports device in the form of a plastic disc with a diameter of 20-25 cm, used for throwing and hanging.. There are several sports associated with the Frisbee outfit. A type of team and action sport that is played with people or with animals, including dogs. Band-Aid - bend aid lexical unit refers to an adhesive device that is tied over an open wound received by an athlete or glued to prevent injury. More than this device is used in martial arts to prevent injuries to the ankle. These two terms PES, formed by the Coinej method, are among the fifty-four neologisms common in English.

Lexical units of PES, formed in the Uzbek language using the koinej method, can be found in national and local sports, folk games. For example, lanka is a game weapon with a heavy metal (lead, coin, etc.) attached to the back of a piece of long-haired leather, and the name given to it; varrak - the name given to a game in which a reed or stick is made by placing a stick of cloth or paper on top of it by placing it in a symbolic or pictorial form. Chillak is the name of a children's game played with one long and one short wooden stick. The short wooden stick that wraps the leaf strip is also called a chillak.

Another way to form a word in Koinej is **eponym** (s).An eponym is the formation of a new word based on the name of the inventor of the new object or concept discovered. Such lexical units related to PES are often formed on the basis of the names of the performers of the new sport, the persons who have developed new rules in certain sports. The lexical units created in this way are international lexical units that enrich the vocabulary of any language and any terminological system. For example, the term panenka is a lexical unit of PES, derived from the Czech footballer Antonin Panenko, a Czech footballer, after an eleven-meter penalty kick against Germany in the 1976 European Football Championship.

Skilled masters of sports of the English and Uzbek peoples also managed to include their names in the terminology of PES and the dictionary of the field. For

example; Derwael-Fenton is the name of a movement in the Darville-Fenton gymnastics double uneven barbell. This eponym was given in honor of British representatives Nina Derwael and Georgia-Mae Fenton masters of sports. Downie - Downy represents the name of a new rotational movement in the form of uneven bars (uneven bars) of gymnastics. Awarded in honor of Master of Sports Rebecca Downie. Henman (“Henman Hill”) - Xinmen (“Hinmen Hill”) is the name given to a method of taking the ball in front of the net by passing the ball in a tennis game. This method is named in honor of the famous tennis player Tim Henman. Peel - The elephant was awarded in honor of Walter Peel, who used the defender's effective ball-raising technique in attacking croquet.

We can see that all of the PES eponyms above are directly related to the names of the UK representatives. As a result of the analysis of our research, we were able to identify eponyms associated with the names of talented Uzbek athletes among the terminology units of international PES.

For example: Chusovitina - Chusovitina is a full-circle binary somersault named after Oksana Chusovitina from Uzbekistan. Chusovitina - When using the term Chusovitina, it is advisable to take into account the direction of the sport. Because this term is used in different areas of gymnastics. Blending - blending method. English and Uzbek are languages with a constant dynamics of development, constantly evolving.

From the twentieth century, the process of naming new technological and socio-cultural realities in English with lexical units created by the method of blending - blending (mixing) began. One of the methods of word formation in English, where productivity is low, is the blending method. It has been found that the new lexical units that emerge through this method have three different appearances. In the system of terminological units of PES, we can give the following examples, formed by the method of blending - blending:

The first view is the lexical units formed by combining the components of two independent words, i.e. by adding the first syllable of the first word with the last (two) syllables of the second word: chill (cool) + relax = chillax (to calm down);

engine (car engine) + hotel = motel television + television + broadcast (telecast) = telecast (telecast); television (television) + photogenic (person who looks good in a picture or movie) = telegenic (person who looks good on a TV screen); camera + recorder = camcorder (camcorder that captures and displays images at the same time).

The second view is formed by the combination of only the main syllables of two independent words: biography (biography) + picture (picture, image) = biopic (biographical picture, frame).

The third view is that one-syllable words are taken as a whole and the last syllables of the second unit are added: fan (fan) + magazine (magazine) = fanzine (amateur magazine); sports + sportscast = sportscast.

Clipping is a method of shortening. In linguistics, the creation of new lexical units by dropping one or more syllables of words is called the clipping method. This method is close to the blending method in many respects. The main difference between the two events is that the abbreviation-clipping method is performed on only one word or phrase. German linguist H. Marshand (Marchand) argues that the new lexical units created by this method serve to enrich the vocabulary in accordance with the principles of linguistics and rightly so.

In the study, based on the specificity of PES terms created by the method of abbreviation-clipping in English, we found it expedient to study them in four types:

1) initial clipping - by shortening (dropping) the front syllable in the word structure: parachute (parachute) - chute (vertical corridor for sliding); university (university) - varsity (university sports team). An e- α -type change occurred as a result of an assimilation event within the variance unit;

2) final clipping - with shortening (dropping) of the back syllable in the word structure: cablegram (telegram) - cable (thick rope, rope); gymnastics (gymnastics) - gym (gymnastics hall); memorandum (document for note) - memo (protocol, protocol); examination (check) - exam (test, test); ticket (ticket) - tick (account); captain (captain) - cap (hat, cap); referee (referee) - ref (reference); umpire (judge) - ump (judge);

3) medial clipping - occurs with a shortening of the middle syllable (s) in the word structure: celebrities - celebrities; fantasy (fantasy) - fans (assumption, fan);

4) complex clipping - occurs as a result of shortening of compound words of complex and mixed type: organization man (organizer, person) - org-man (organizer). This method makes it easier to pronounce phrases and compound words that are considered to be more complex in English.

The abbreviation method in Uzbek is not very effective. It is natural that we find terms created in this way in the terminological systems of different fields. Most of them are formed using Russian or other language units. In this sense, the regulation of terms related to PES and their concrete interpretation, clarification of the field to which they belong, providing etymological information, consistent recording serve to perfect the adequate interpretation of terms in translation. This, in turn, leads to the perfection of both annotated and bilingual dictionaries in the field.

Back-formation is a method of back-formation. Another type of word formation in English is the back-formation method. The literal translation of the concept of back-formation is back - ort, back, formation - formation, formation. According to the principles of this method, words occur as a result of unusual abbreviations for the transformation of a morphologically specific word (category) into another word (category). In the English system of physical education and sports terminology there are also terms and neologisms formed in this way. For example: The word emote (feeling) is formed from the word Emotion, and N → V, that is, a verb from the noun phrase; evaluation - evaluate, i.e. N → V; mentor (mentor) - mentee (to advise), i.e. N → V; commentator - commentate, i.e. N → V; manipulation - manipulate, i.e. N → V; goaltender (goalie in hockey) - goaltend (to protect the goal), i.e. N → V; spectator (spectator) - spectate, i.e. N → V. Most of the words that form the basis of lexical units formed by the method of backformation in English came from Latin and Greek.

The results of the analysis of sources in Uzbek linguistics showed that in the Uzbek language there were no words formed by the method of back-formation. The Uzbek language contains some similar words in the structure and neologisms of PES.

However, they are accepted as a method of clipping borrowed words - borrowing or shortening.

Conversion - a method of conversion. As important is the role of extra linguistic factors in the expansion of vocabulary, the internal (linguistic) capabilities of language is just as important. Another way to use the internal capabilities of the language is the conversion method. In English, words formed by this method are present in the terminological systems of almost all fields. In English, most lexical units are reflected in various dictionaries because of the prevalence of word formation through the conversion method. In this method, the external form of lexical units does not change, but a change occurs in their morphological category. In the linguistic literature, conversion is defined as “word formation without affixes”, “inflectional method of word formation”, “word formation in phonetic and morphological methods”, “syntactic derivation”, “zero-affixation method”, “transposition” and given the names.

The study found that the following lexical units related to the English PES were created by the conversion method.

A → N: green → green (points awarded to a ball that falls into a golf hole); final → final (final game of the tournament or final exam);

Verb → at - V → N: to hit (hit) → hit (blow); to whistle (whistle) → whistle (whistle); to alert → alert;

to attack → attack; to command → command; to experience → experience; to hope → hope; to judge → judge; to run → run; to start → start; to turn → turn

Adj. → verb - A → V: dirty → dirty; dry → dry.

At → verb - N → V: eye → to eye (to look); ship → to ship (to load on a boat or ship); spear → to spear (to aim).

It should be noted that it is natural that the converted English PES terms have a semantic and syntactic character specific to another word group. This creates complex and confusing situations in the translation of materials related to the field. In this case, the need for perfectly glossary dictionaries naturally increases even more.

In the course of the research it was found out that in the Uzbek language PES terminology lexical units created by this method are formed in two different ways. Including:

1) without changing the form - in the form of a verb (in the stem) → horse: kurash (to fight) → kurash (game name); swelling (swelling) → swelling (injury);

2) Conversion of simple verbs with the suffixes -sh, -ish, -uv, -ov in the form of a verb → noun: call, call, check, show, deceive, deceive, take, surround, process, change, interest and others.

Multiple processes - mixed type method. Although this method is not very productive in the construction of lexical units related to English PES, it is distinguished by the participation of various methods in the construction of words. WHO In the mixed type method: Problems with the family have snowballed (translation: Problems with the family have become snowballed). Suffix → playmaker; add method → suffix → goalkeeper; mix method → suffix → midfielder; add method → suffix → footballer; suffix → suffix → advisory; assimilation → suffix → add method → multiple process units such as quarterback. Therefore, various methods are distinguished in the formation and development of PES terms in the English language.

There is a disparity in the methods of word formation in English, in particular, the occurrence of conversion, abbreviation, backformation, phonological phenomena in the terminological system is mainly characteristic of the English PES terminological system. These events are very rare in Uzbek. In English terminology, the method of borrowing is studied as an integral part of borrowings due to its nature.

References:

1. Ирискулов М. Тилшуносликка кириш. –Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1992. – 252 б.

2. Whyte J. Ch. History of the British turf from the earliest period to the present day, Volume I. – London,1840. – P. 36, 385, 400.

3.Yule G. The Study of Language-IV. – Cambridge University Press. –

2006. – P. 51-66.

Dictionaries

1. Active study of English. – Moscow, 1988. –P. 710

2. Boatner M.T., Gates J.E. A Dictionary of American Idioms. – New York, 2005. – P. 452.

3.Hornby A. S. The Advanced Learner’s Dictionary of Current English. – London, 1974. – P. 750.

Internet resources

1. championat.asia

2. [electronizohlilug’at.uz](http://electronizohlilug.at.uz)

3. <http://lex.uz/docs/3578244>

4. <http://www.etymonline.com/index>